

EXERCISES FOR READING AND WRITING

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We all know that today it is impossible to organize a modern and communicative lesson without exercises and assignments. Exercises and assignments are important in the learning process and are an integral and solid part of an effective foreign language learning process. By completing exercises and assignments, we will practice and apply our theoretical knowledge. Therefore, exercises and assignments serve to apply the learned theoretical knowledge in practice, knowledge turns into skills during training. Among them, there are many exercises aimed at developing reading and writing skills.

Extensive reading, writing, or related exercises in and out of the classroom can help language learners improve their reading and writing skills. When preparing a lesson plan, teachers need to take into account the different ages and levels of students. Teachers should use student-related contexts as much as possible, as this will help them motivate students to

ABSTRACT

In this article, the effective use of exercises and tasks aimed at developing modern-communicative reading and writing skills in the course of teaching foreign languages in foreign language classes, in which detailed information is given about the differences between exercises and tasks, their specific characteristics and types.

read. In some cases, students have complained that they find the reading or writing exercises boring and do not want to read the texts you have given them. This is one of the problems in foreign language teaching. An actual question arises as to what should be paid attention to in this process. Choose the same types of texts that students enjoy reading outside of the classroom and develop pre-reading and post-reading activities to go with them. As a result, they enjoy reading and writing exercises because they are already familiar with the material. Below, we will analyze focused exercises that improve reading skills.

Methods

Basically, reading takes two forms: a) just for pleasure; b) to obtain information to a certain extent. Both methods develop language learners' reading skills. Teaching reading skills can be easy when taught with consistent practice and strategies. Without proper strategies, study tests become

boring for many people. In the classroom, teachers use a variety of learning exercises. In this process, they can use various guides, to-do lists, course books, blogs, websites, newspapers and magazines. Students should be taught six strategies to improve their reading ability in a variety of contexts. Below we will cover the steps necessary for studying these six methods.

Results

Prediction exercise - guessing or predicting when translating from English.

Preparatory task by predicting the genre and information in the text before reading it. Pay attention to headlines, pictures, and other key details to determine what the text is about. In this process, learners complete a task based on prior knowledge and experience. The teacher can set preparatory tasks by asking general questions to get familiar with the lesson or passage being worked on.

Skimming exercise - focusing on the most important information in a given passage.

A quick reading process to get an overview of the passage. While skimming, ask your students to underline nouns, prepositions, and conjunctions to easily identify general ideas and concepts.

Scanning exercise - determining the main content to be understood from the text.

It is done to get the exact information of the piece. Here, students should be taught to collect specific information to underline the text to get date, year, name, important vocabulary, etc. You will read the marked points in the text to find your answers. For example, if your readers are reading a museum website to find out how much the entrance fee is, they can use this strategy.

Cohesive devices exercise - analysis based on units that help to connect the sentences given in the text.

Look for conjunctions and prepositions such as "on the other hand," "directly," and "although" that make the reader want to take the text in a different direction.

Guessing the meaning of vocabulary exercise - to guess the meaning of the words unfamiliar to the students given in the passage in connection with the situation.

Discussion

After reading the text, your intermediate students will find some words that they do not understand. In this case, students are asked to think about the linguistic context of each word. A word or dictionary can be used before and after the text to get information about the meaning of new words.

As you can see, there are many exercises that can be used to improve the reading skills of foreign language learners. There are also many writing-related exercises and tasks in language teaching.

When preparing for writing exercises, we will consider how to make them as meaningful as possible. You can do this by thinking about your audience, situation, and purpose. This can be a task for younger students, such as writing a story, or for older students writing about their personal lives. Often in the classroom, it is also easy to ask students to complete an assignment from a syllabus or coursebook without thinking about the above three things. In the future, try to make this a regular feature of any writing task - define the context, purpose, and audience before starting the task. You can figure them all out together, or the students decide for themselves. Whichever way you try, it should make the writing more meaningful. Planning ideas logically exercise - logically planning a sequence of ideas.

Careful planning helps students place the text in a logical sequence and in an order that is easy to read. The beginning should be like the beginning of the text that will interest the readers. Each "piece" of text should naturally lead to the next. And, of course, there should be a logical conclusion at the end of the written work.

Writing accurately exercise - correct writing exercise.

If the text is concise, it means that the most effective words are used. Writers often fill sentences with words that are poorly chosen and can be removed or replaced. By getting feedback, editing, and revising their writing after a day or two, students can develop the skills to spot words that shouldn't be in the text.

Paragraphing exercise - write your personal thoughts in paragraphs based on a topic.

Conclusion

Effective use of paragraphs helps readers follow the written work. In general, each paragraph should have its own idea. A large block of text without paragraphs can confuse and annoy readers. Paragraphs are difficult to read if sentences are thrown together without connecting words or phrases. As sentences must be linked within paragraphs, paragraphs must also be linked. When the reader moves from one paragraph to another, words and phrases can be used to help with the transition if the reference is not clear.

There are many types of exercises you can do to help your students develop reading and writing skills, such as grammar, vocabulary, sentence structure, and coherence.

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